

THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE IMAGE ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION WITH TRUST AS A MEDIATING VARIABLE IN THE NEW PRODUCT LAUNCHING (NPL) GENTLE GEN AT MAYORA INDAH TBK COMPANY

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Abstract

Currently, the FMCG industry is experiencing increasing competition, which encourages businesses/companies to continuously seek innovation, particularly through the introduction of new products. However, many new products fail due to a lack of differentiation and a lack of initial consumer demand. Corporate image is a key factor in determining the success of a new product launch. This is important because a positive public image can influence public opinion and foster consumer trust. This study focuses on PT Mayora Indah Tbk, emphasizing the introduction of the Gentle Gen liquid detergent product launched in 2022 as a strategic business move to market for a new product. The purpose of this study is to determine how corporate image influences consumer purchasing intentions, with trust acting as a mediating variable. This study uses a quantitative methodology using an online questionnaire survey. The sample was selected using purposive sampling, with respondents meeting requirements such as being at least 18 years old, making purchasing decisions for household goods, and having a basic understanding of the Mayora brand or Gentle Gen products. Using SmartPLS 4.0 software, data collected from a minimum of 100 respondents will be analyzed using Partial Least Squares (PLS). It is predicted that the research findings will demonstrate a beneficial and substantial impact of corporate reputation on consumer purchase intentions, both directly and indirectly through the trust variable. It is expected that the trust variable will function as a mediating element that strengthens this relationship. From an academic perspective, this study will explain the function of trust as a mediator in new product introductions in FMCG companies in Indonesia. This study provides useful insights for Mayora's marketing plan to increase the market success of Gentle Gen from a realistic perspective.

Keywords: *Corporate Image, Trust, Purchase Intention, New Product Launch, Mayora, Gentle Gen*

Introduction

Competition is currently increasingly fierce and dynamic in the business world, especially in the *consumer goods industry*. To ensure company continuity and achieve sustainable growth, every company strives to continuously innovate. One strategic step in this innovation effort is launching new products. According to Kotler and Keller (2020), launching new products is a very important strategy for companies to remain relevant amidst very tight market competition. According to some experts, the failure rate of new product launches is still very high, reaching around 40%, caused by a lack of differentiation and a failure to build consumer purchasing interest from the start (Grewal et al., 2020). New products often become "*me-too products*" because they do not offer clear and different advantages, benefits, or value compared to existing competitors. Failure to build purchasing interest from the start is also related to the strategy. product launch Weaknesses stem from the product being offered being in a relatively new category on the market. This includes unclear *positioning*, ineffective marketing communications, inappropriate pricing, or distribution that doesn't reach all regions. One of the largest *consumer goods companies* in Indonesia is PT Mayora Indah Tbk. Mayora has a very strong and well-known brand in various circles with a very wide product diversification, such as Kopiko, Torabika, Beng-Beng, Energen, Le Minerale, Teh Pucuk Harum and many more flagship products. Mayora's corporate image has been built for decades as a reliable, innovative company

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that understands the tastes and desires of consumers in Indonesia. In 2022, Mayora launched a new product, Gentle Gen. Gentle Gen is a *homecare product* in the form of a liquid detergent. Gentle Gen is a pioneer of plant-based detergents with the advantage of providing cleaning power derived from natural plants without labas substances so that it leaves hands softer and the resulting fragrance is long-lasting. Gentle Gen is a *new product launch* in a new category or *segment* for Mayora which previously only produced *healthy food, instant food, and coffee products*. Mayora innovates by creating innovative products with an environmentally friendly and good skin *positioning*. In addition, consumers who do not have much information about the quality of Gentle Gen as a new product make Mayora's long-established corporate image an indirect guarantee to consumers that Gentle Gen is worth buying and using, even though the product is still relatively new on the market.

The launch of the Gentle Gen product is interesting to analyze because, although Mayora has a strong corporate reputation, this product is in a relatively new category for them, so this is what makes Mayora have to compete with previous products that are already in the market. Furthermore, the relationship between corporate image and consumer purchasing interest is often not direct, so the existence of trust as a connecting factor is very important. A positive corporate image can help build trust among consumers. When consumers are convinced that Mayora is a company that has good quality, that trust will be transferred to its new product, namely Gentle Gen. Thus, trust acts as a bridge that strengthens the impact of corporate image on consumer purchasing interest. This is because consumers tend to assume that companies with a good reputation will not release disappointing products.

The better a company's image, the more likely it is that the products and services launched will be accepted by the market, as demonstrated in research by Kotler and Keller (2020). Furthermore, trust in a company's image is a strong factor when consumers want to purchase new products, especially in categories involving functional risks, such as detergents related to cleanliness and skin safety. According to Kotler and Keller (2020), purchase intention is a consumer's tendency to purchase a product or service offered by a company. If consumers lack trust in a company, they will have no intention of purchasing its products. Especially for new products, where information is still limited, trust is a key consideration. Research by Tiara et al. (2021) found that trust positively influences consumer purchase intention. The research question is how does a company's image influence consumer purchase intention? which has been built strongly can influence consumer purchasing interest in *the new product launch* at the company, namely the Gentle Gen product.

Figure 1. Liquid Detergent Sales Trend Graph

Source: Internal Company Data

Based on the Gentle Gen sales chart above (March 2025 – January 2026 period), it can be explained that Gentle Gen's sales are lower compared to several major competitors in the liquid detergent category. The product with the largest market share is Soklin which consistently dominates with a range of around 60–70% throughout the period. Meanwhile, other competitors such as SoSoft and Rinso also show fairly stable performance with a gradual increasing trend. Compared to competitor products, Gentle Gen's sales are in the range of around 10–13%, which indicates that although this product has been able to gain a certain market share, its position is still below brands that have long been known by consumers. This phenomenon can be explained because the Gentle Gen product is still in a new category in the market. Gentle Gen is still in the early stages of the product life cycle, namely the introduction

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stage, where the level of consumer awareness (*brand awareness*), trust in the product, and customer loyalty are still in the process of being formed. In the context of this research, it shows that the company's image and consumer trust in new products are important elements that can influence increased purchasing interest and ultimately have the potential to increase Gentle Gen's market share in the future. The influence of corporate image on purchasing intention in *new product launches* is not new in research. Foroudi (2020) concluded in his study that a positive corporate image directly increases consumer interest in purchasing the product. This statement is further supported by research by Anwar (2021), who stated that in the banking services sector, corporate image is the strongest indicator of customer purchasing intention. Existing literature has demonstrated a significant positive relationship between the two variables. In the context of new product launches, a study by Gupta et al. (2020) showed that consumers are more receptive to innovations from companies they know and trust.

This is because corporate image serves as a "signal" that reduces the perceived risk inherent in new products. Meanwhile, research by Chen & Lee (2022) on health food products found that corporate brand equity *significantly* influences perceived value and purchasing intention for newly launched products. Based on the literature review, several *research gaps* underlie this study. First, the specific context of the research object. Most previous research has been conducted in the banking and aviation sectors, or even on established products (Prasetya and Santoso, 2020; Sari and Wijaya, 2023). Research specifically examining the role of corporate image in the successful launch of new FMCG products in Indonesia, particularly at Mayora, remains very limited. Second, the measurable mediating variable. Although trust is often cited as a mediator, there has been little empirical research in recent years (2020-2025) that quantitatively tests and validates the mediating power of trust in the relationship between Mayora's corporate image and purchase intention for a specific new product like Gentle Gen. Third, consumer response to brand diversification is crucial. Gentle Gen represents a significant diversification for Mayora. This research will fill this gap by analyzing the strength of corporate image. can be applied to product categories that are "new" to the company that have not been fully answered by previous research. Based on the background and identification of *the gap analysis* presented, this study aims to analyze the direct influence of Mayora's corporate image on consumer purchasing interest in the new product, namely Gentle Gen. Thus, this study not only tests the existing relationship but also deepens understanding by placing it in a specific context in terms of the launch of the new product Gentle Gen at the Mayora company.

Literature Review

Corporate Image and Purchase Intention

Corporate image is a picture formed in the minds of consumers and serves as a tool for assessing an organization. Wahyuni et al. (2019) revealed that a positive corporate image can help foster the development of internal creativity and have a broader impact on society. A good corporate image is a valuable asset for a company because it can shape customers' positive views of the company's communication and operations, particularly in terms of customer treatment. The stronger the corporate image, the greater the likelihood that the products or services offered will be accepted by the market. Meanwhile, according to Kotler and Keller (2020), purchasing interest is a consumer's desire to purchase a particular product or service. This is often triggered by various external factors, such as marketing activities or environmental impacts. Purchasing interest also describes the social process involving decisions made by individuals, groups, and organizations in assessing and acquiring goods or services through purchasing transactions. According to a study conducted by Pratama (2023), corporate image has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions. The findings of this study indicate that corporate image influences purchasing decisions by 33%. This is in line with the findings of Noviningsih et al. (2022), who explain that corporate image influences consumer purchasing decisions. This study explains that the better the corporate image, the higher consumer purchasing interest in the products or services offered. This is also supported by research by Mandagi et al. (2018), which states that improving corporate image will be accompanied by an increase in consumer purchasing interest. This finding aligns with research by Khayru (2021), which explains that in order to increase consumer purchasing interest, the company's image also needs to be improved in the community. The same finding is also explained in research by Misbachull et al. (2021), which shows a significant influence of corporate image on consumer purchasing interest. A positive corporate image will be stored in consumers' memories and have

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a positive impact on their purchasing intentions. Based on the explanations from these various studies, there is a positive relationship between corporate image and purchasing interest. So the resulting hypothesis is:

H₁ : Corporate image has a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest.

Corporate Image and Trust

A positive corporate image can be the foundation for building trust. When customers perceive a company as capable, responsible, and reputable, they are more likely to trust it. Trust is a customer's willingness to trust a brand despite potential risks. This trust is shaped by the expectations conveyed by the brand, which ultimately have a positive impact on consumers (Noviningsih et al., 2022). Considering this, trust plays a crucial role in increasing product value and competitiveness. According to Delgado (2019), trust reflects customers' expectations of a brand's reliability and goodwill. This statement aligns with research by Lin et al. (2021) in the service sector, which explains that a company's image has a significant positive impact on customer trust in the products or services offered.

Kamaruddin et al. (2021) explain that corporate image influences consumer trust. The findings of this study indicate that the better the public's assessment of a company, the greater consumer trust in it. This is in line with Pratama et al. (2023), who found that corporate image has a significant positive impact on building consumer trust. Furthermore, Setyawan et al. (2021) also emphasized that corporate image plays a significant role in building consumer trust. A positive corporate image not only attracts consumer interest but also strengthens positive perceptions and increases consumer trust in the company. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship between corporate image and consumer trust. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₂ : Corporate image has a positive effect on trust.

Trust and Purchase Interest

Trust is crucial in any business activity. A transaction between two or more parties can proceed smoothly if all parties respect and have confidence in one another. In the business world, trust is not simply formed; it must be cultivated from the company's inception (Prasetya et al., 2020). This trust serves as a key driver of purchase intention. Buyers will be less likely to purchase products from companies they perceive as untrustworthy. This becomes even more crucial for new products, where available information is still limited, making trust a key factor considered by consumers. Tiara et al. (2021) in their study found that trust indicators positively impact consumer purchase intention. This explains that consumers with high levels of trust are more likely to purchase a product. These results align with research by Dyah et al. (2020), which found that trust indicators have a significant influence on consumer purchase intention. Furthermore, research by Riski et al. (2019) also highlights that trust is a factor influencing purchasing decisions. When consumers feel confident in a product or company, it increases their desire to make a purchase. Furthermore, a study conducted by Pratama et al. (2023) further supports this finding, explaining that trust can influence consumer purchase intentions. These two factors are interrelated and have a positive impact on each other. Based on the existing research results, it is concluded that trust has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions. Therefore, the research hypothesis is as follows:

H₃ : Trust has a positive effect on buying interest.

The Role of Trust as a Mediating Variable

The direct relationship between corporate image and purchase intention has been shown to have a positive impact. However, recent research suggests that this relationship is indirect. A strong, established corporate image acts as a reliable signal, which consumers cognitively process to build trust. This trust ultimately triggers customers' interest in purchasing goods. This is in line with research by Pratama et al. (2023), who stated that platform image (Tokopedia, Shopee, and Lazada) significantly influences consumer purchase intention, but this influence is entirely dependent on trust. Therefore, only a positive image can encourage transactions if consumers have confidence in the platform's data security and honesty in transactions. Consumer trust serves as an important mediator in the relationship between corporate image and consumer purchase intention. Based on the research findings of Khan et al. (2020), trust is the primary mediator between consumer perceptions and their intention to make a transaction. When consumers already have trust, they are more likely to be interested in purchasing the product offered. Thus, corporate image acts as an initial variable, while trust functions as a mental process that can transform positive perceptions into intentions to act and drive purchase intention. In line with research by Kamaruddin et al. (2021), which explains that trust can be a link between corporate image and consumer purchasing interest. Setyawan et al. (2021) also revealed that consumer purchasing interest tends to increase when a company has a positive image in the eyes of consumers, which in turn can foster trust in the products and services offered. This indicates that trust

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functions as a connecting variable between the impact of corporate image and consumer purchasing interest. In Pratama et al.'s (2023) research on the banking industry, trust also functions as a connecting variable. This means that corporate image not only has a direct impact but also an indirect one through building trust among customers, ultimately increasing consumer interest in conducting transactions with the company. Referring to previous studies, the resulting hypothesis is:

H₄ : Trust mediates between corporate image and consumer purchasing interest.

Figure of the Relationship Model between Variables to be Tested

Figure 2. Research Framework

The flow of thought on the relationship between variables

Corporate Image (X) → Consumer Trust (Z)

Mechanism : A positive company image such as a good reputation, social responsibility, transparency, and quality of service can build trust *in* consumers.

Consumer Confidence (Z) → Consumer Purchase Interest (Y)

Mechanism : Trust is the foundation of purchasing decisions. Consumers who trust a product tend to feel safer making transactions, which can increase their purchasing intentions.

Company Image (X) → Consumer Purchase Interest (Y)

Mechanism : Corporate image not only influences trust, but can also directly influence the perception of value and attractiveness of products or services, thereby increasing purchasing interest.

Theory of Planned Behavior states that behavior is guided by an individual's intention *to* perform the behavior (Suntornsan, et al., 2022). Intention is the antecedent or proximal (closest) cause of behavior (Ajzen, 2020). The stronger a person's desire to perform a behavior, the more likely they are to engage in that behavior (Norisnita and Indriati, 2022). *The Theory of Planned Behavior* (TPB) emphasizes the role of trust as a driver of behavioral intention . *Theory of Planned Behavior* This theory was chosen because it explains how a positive corporate image can create trust among individuals, thus generating consumer purchasing interest. This is relevant for researching purchasing behavior that requires a sense of security and trust, and provides a strong theoretical basis for the relationship that the higher consumer trust in a company with a positive image, the higher the purchasing interest for the products or services offered by that company. In the TPB framework , a positive corporate image plays a strong role as an antecedent, especially in shaping "attitudes toward behavior" and "perceived behavioral control" . Corporate image is the consumer's perception of the Mayora company as a whole, including reputation, credibility, quality, and social responsibility. When Mayora, as a large and well-known company, launches a new product, namely the Gentle Gen product, consumers will tend to have a positive reaction to the behavior of purchasing the new Gentle Gen product. A positive corporate image builds strong *behavioral beliefs* and ultimately forms a *positive* attitude towards purchasing a new product, namely the Gentle Gen product. While perceived *behavioral control* When consumers find it easier to decide to purchase new products from companies with a good reputation to reduce risk, the company's image strengthens perceived behavioral control *by* providing confidence and reducing uncertainty. Mayora's positive corporate image acts as a key driver influencing consumer confidence. This confidence is then reflected in trust . High trust serves as a mediating variable that strengthens the two main determinants in the TPB theory. By developing a positive attitude and high behavioral control, purchase interest in new Gentle Gen products becomes stronger. In other words, trust can strengthen positive perceptions of the company, thus generating interest in purchasing Gentle Gen products.

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Research methods

Types of research

This study employed a quantitative method, meaning using numbers to examine the relationship between variables. This method was chosen because it aligns with the research objective of examining the influence of corporate image on consumer purchasing intention, with trust as a mediating variable (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Data were obtained through a questionnaire survey distributed directly to respondents online using social media platforms, one of which is Instagram. The questionnaire distribution period was from January 6, 2026, to January 20, 2026.

Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

Population: The population studied were consumers who were aware of or were likely to use liquid detergent products, especially Gentle Gen from PT Mayora Indah Tbk, which is located in the Java Island region.

Sample: respondents were selected from the population with the following criteria:

- Minimum age 18 years.
- Be a decision maker in purchasing household products (e.g. detergent).
- Have you ever heard of Gentle Gen or know PT Mayora Indah Tbk.

The sampling criteria were as follows: first, a minimum age of 18 years, as this is a measure of maturity in decision-making. Second, relevance to the research product, specifically household products, specifically detergent. Third, brand awareness, in terms of knowledge about the Mayora company, was crucial. This was to ensure respondents had a basis for assessing the company's image and Gentle Gen products. Sampling Technique: Using a *non-probability* sampling method with a *purposive sampling approach*. This was chosen because researchers only require respondents who meet certain criteria and are relevant to the research focus (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). One method applied to calculate the minimum sample size in the PLS path model is a method known as the 10 times rule (Hair et al., 2019). In this approach, the minimum sample size is calculated by multiplying 10 by the total number of influential variables. In this study, there are 3 variables and the total indicators of each variable reaches 10, so the minimum number of respondents required is 100 people.

Operational Definition of Variables and Measurement

Corporate Image (X): Overall consumer perception of PT Mayora, including reputation, credibility, and general impression of the company. This variable is measured using four adapted indicators from Foroudi et al. (2020) and Kotler and Keller (2020), namely company quality and reliability, innovation and pioneering, social and environmental responsibility, and brand strength and recognition. Trust (Z): Consumer confidence that Mayora is honest, reliable, and has good intentions in presenting Gentle Gen products. This variable is measured by 3 adapted indicators from Delgado (2019) and Noviningsih et al. (2022), namely company honesty and integrity, company competence and expertise, and company good intentions towards consumers. *behavioral* tendencies and intentions to purchase or consider Gentle Gen products. This variable is measured using three adapted indicators from Kotler and Keller (2020), namely the intention to try or purchase, the likelihood of recommending to others, and preference for Gentle Gen products over competitors.

Data collection technique

The primary data collection was conducted through an online questionnaire distributed through social media platforms. The questionnaire was structured using a 5-point Likert scale, with the following details: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree. This structured questionnaire consisted of three sections: the first section included screening questions and respondent demographic data; the second section included questions to measure corporate image, trust, and purchasing intention. Meanwhile, the third section provided an open space for respondents to receive suggestions and input.

Data Analysis Techniques

Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis is a multivariate statistical method used to analyze the relationship between dependent variables and independent variables (Abdillah, 2015).

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1. Measurement Model

- Convergent Validity: This measurement is carried out by paying attention to the factor loading value, which functions to test the level of relationship between constructs and latent variables.
- Discriminative Validity: This test aims to compare the relationship between indicators and their latent variables with the relationship with other latent variables.
- *Composite Reliability* : Reliability testing is carried out using two approaches, namely Cronbach's alpha and Composite reliability.

2. Structural Model

Used to explain causal (cause-effect) or predictive relationships between latent variables (constructs), whether the influence of the hypothesized construct is significant or not (Yamins (2011).

-R-Square analysis is carried out to assess how much influence the dependent variable has on the independent variable and also the mediating variable.

- Goodness of Fit (GoF): Goodness of Fit testing can be seen from the R-Square value (Ghozali, 2015) where the GoF assessment criteria consist of 0.10 for the small GoF category, 0.25 for the medium GoF category, and 0.36 for the large GoF category.

Descriptive statistical analysis: to describe and explain the characteristics of each respondent and the answer profile of each variable.

Path analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4.0. The PLS method was chosen because of its ability to test models involving mediating variables and does not require the assumption of normal distribution in the data (Hair et al., 2019).

Mediation test: to test the role of trust as a mediator (H4), the *Specific Indirect Effect method* in PLS will be used. According to research by Hair et al (2019), mediation is considered to occur if the indirect effect (Corporate Image → Trust → Purchase Intention) is significant, while the direct effect (Corporate Image → Purchase Intention) can be insignificant (full mediation) or remain significant with a smaller value (partial mediation).

Results and Discussion

Respondent Characteristics

The discussion of respondent characteristics in this study explains the profile of consumers who participated in the study entitled " **The Influence of Corporate Image on Consumer Purchase Intention with Trust as a Mediating Variable on the Launch of New Products (NPL) Gentle Gen at PT Mayora Indah Tbk**". From the data obtained, most of the respondents were women, as many as 74 people or 67.3%, while male respondents numbered 36 people or 32.7%. The dominance of female respondents in this study can be explained because detergent products are generally related to household needs which in many times are still more often managed by women as the main decision makers in purchasing household products. This shows that the perception of corporate image and the level of trust in new products such as Gentle Gen are influenced by consumer groups who have high involvement in household cleaning products.

In terms of age, the majority of respondents were in the 26–35 age range with a total of 67 people or 60.9%, followed by the 18–25 age group with 34 people or 30.9%. The 36–45 age group numbered 8 people or 7.3%, while the 46–55 age group only had 1 person or 0.9%. This indicates that most respondents are in the productive age category and are relatively active in carrying out consumption activities and are open to new products in the market. This age group generally has a higher level of information literacy and is more responsive to company reputation and brand trust, so that the company image factor can be an important consideration in shaping purchasing interest in new products such as Gentle Gen. Based on educational level, the majority of respondents had a bachelor's degree (77 people, or 70%), with a high school education of 25 people (22.8%), while respondents with diplomas and master's degrees each numbered 4 people (3.6%). The high level of educational attainment of respondents indicates that the majority of participants have a fairly good ability to evaluate information about the company and the products offered. In the context of this study, a relatively high level of education can influence how consumers assess a company's image and build trust in new products, as consumers with higher education tend to be more critical in considering the quality, company reputation, and credibility of information before deciding to purchase a product. Furthermore, based on domicile area, the largest number of respondents came from West Java, with 41 people or 37.3%. The next position was occupied by respondents from DKI Jakarta and East Java, each with 27 people or 24.55%. Respondents from

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Central Java numbered 11 people or 10%, while from DI Yogyakarta there were 3 people or 2.7%, and the fewest came from Banten with 1 person or 0.9%. This distribution of respondents indicates that the study has covered several major provinces on the island of Java, which are centers of economic activity and consumption in Indonesia. These regions also have a high level of consumer product penetration, making it relevant to observe how the corporate image of PT Mayora Indah Tbk influences consumer trust and purchasing interest in the new product Gentle Gen. Thus, the characteristics of the respondents in this study indicate that the majority of participants are female consumers, are of productive age, have a relatively high level of education, and come from areas with high consumption activity. This can provide important context in understanding the relationship between corporate image, trust, and purchasing interest in the new product, namely the Gentle Gen product.

Table 1. Respondent Demographics

Gender		
Gender	Amount	Percentage
Man	36	32.7%
Woman	74	67.3%
Total	110	100.0%
Age		
Age	Amount	Percentage
18-25 Years	34	30.9%
26-35 Years	67	60.9%
36-45 Years	8	7.3%
46-55 Years	1	0.9%
Total	110	100.0%
Last education		
Last education	Amount	Percentage
SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	25	22.7%
Diploma	4	3.6%
Bachelor	77	70.0%
Postgraduate	4	3.6%
Total	110	100.0%
Work		
Work	Amount	Percentage
Students	12	10.9%
Private employees	68	61.8%
Government employees	5	4.5%
Self-employed	13	11.8%
Housewife	8	7.3%
Teacher	2	1.8%
Lecturer	1	0.9%
Doesn't work	1	0.9%
Total	110	100.0%
Domicile		
Domicile	Amount	Percentage
DKI Jakarta	27	24.5%
West Java	41	37.3%
Central Java	11	10.0%
East Java	27	24.5%
DIY Yogyakarta	3	2.7%
Banten	1	0.9%
Total	110	100.0%

Outer Model

A. Convergent Validity

This section will explain the outer model used in the study. The test results show that all indicators in the model have an outer loading value >0.7. This value indicates that each indicator is able to represent its construct well. In addition,

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the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value listed in the table shows that all constructs meet the minimum threshold of 0.5. AVE values above this criterion confirm that the proportion of variance extracted by the indicators is much greater than the variance caused by error. In other words, each question item used is considered valid and able to explain the construct consistently. This confirms that the measurement model is of adequate quality, so that subsequent structural analysis can be interpreted with a higher level of confidence.

Source: PLS-SEM output, 2026

Figure 3. SEM-PLS data processing results diagram

Table 2. Convergent Validity

Variables	Indicator	Ave	Loading Factor
Corporate Image	X1	0.836	0.916
	X2		0.935
	X3		0.891
	X4		0.915
Purchase Interest	Y1	0.879	0.950
	Y2		0.935
	Y3		0.927
Trust	Z1	0.889	0.944
	Z2		0.953
	Z3		0.932

Source: Processed data, 2026

B. Discriminant Validity

HTML

All HTMT values in this study were below the critical limit. This finding indicates that each pair of constructs in the model is able to maintain conceptual separation, so that the relationship between latent variables can be interpreted more confidently without concerns about *overlap*. Based on these results, it is concluded that discriminant validity has been fully met for all constructs used. This means that each construct is able to demonstrate its own unique characteristics and does not overlap in explaining the phenomena studied. The fulfillment of discriminant validity also strengthens the quality of the overall measurement model, so that subsequent structural analysis such as

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hypothesis testing or evaluation of the influence between variables can be carried out with a higher level of reliability. Thus, this model can be relied upon to provide an accurate empirical picture of the relationship between constructs in the study.

Table 3. HTML

	Corporate Image	Purchase Interest	Trust
Corporate Image			
Purchase Interest	0.856		
Trust	0.873	0.848	

Source: Processed data, 2026

Fornell Larcker

In this analysis, the AVE root value for corporate image is 0.914, purchase intention is 0.938, and trust is 0.943. These results indicate that all AVE root values on the main diagonal are higher than the correlation values between constructs outside the diagonal. In more detail, the AVE root value for corporate image (0.914) is greater than its correlation with purchase intention (0.801) and trust (0.819). Similarly, the AVE root value for purchase intention (0.938) exceeds its correlation with corporate image (0.801) and trust (0.794). Furthermore, the trust construct also shows the highest AVE root value (0.943) which exceeds its correlation with corporate image (0.819) and purchase intention (0.794). In other words, these results indicate that each construct has excellent discrimination ability. This construct can provide a stronger explanation of its indicators than its relationship with other constructs. This indicates that there is no excessive conceptual overlap between constructs in the measurement model. Referring to the Fornell-Larcker criteria, it can be concluded that the discriminant validity in the measurement model has been met very satisfactorily.

Table 4. Fornell Larcker

	Corporate Image	Purchase Interest	Trust
Corporate Image	0.914		
Purchase Interest	0.801	0.938	
Trust	0.819	0.794	0.943

Source: Processed data, 2026

Cross Loading

Indicators X1 to X4 show the highest loading values in the corporate image construct, with values ranging from 0.891 to 0.935. These figures are higher than the cross-loadings on the purchase intention construct (0.685–0.805) and trust (0.701–0.815). This indicates that these indicators clearly and consistently measure the corporate image construct. Furthermore, indicators Y1 to Y3 have the highest loading values on the purchase intention construct, with values ranging from 0.927 to 0.950. This value is much higher than the cross-loadings on the corporate image construct (0.739–0.770) and trust (0.719–0.763). This indicates that the purchase intention indicators can differentiate this construct well from other constructs. Indicators Z1 to Z3 have the highest loading values in the trust construct, with values between 0.932 and 0.953. This figure is more dominant than the cross-loadings on corporate image (0.756–0.782) and purchase intention (0.703–0.775). Thus, the trust indicators are proven to measure their constructs accurately and are not mixed with other constructs. The results of the cross-loading analysis explain that all indicators have met the requirements for discriminant validity. This is evident from each indicator having the highest loading value on its original construct with a quite clear difference compared to the cross-loadings on other constructs. Therefore, the measurement model in this study can be considered valid and able to describe each construct validly and discriminatively.

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Table 5. Cross Loading

	Corporate Image	Purchase Interest	Trust
X1	0.916	0.685	0.710
X2	0.935	0.805	0.815
X3	0.891	0.716	0.701
X4	0.915	0.715	0.762
Y1	0.742	0.950	0.719
Y2	0.739	0.935	0.748
Y3	0.770	0.927	0.763
Z1	0.782	0.775	0.944
Z2	0.779	0.703	0.953
Z3	0.756	0.764	0.932

Source: Processed data, 2026

C. Reliability Test

The results of the reliability test in this study indicate that all latent constructs analyzed, namely corporate image, purchase intention, and trust, have a very high level of internal consistency. Referring to the analysis table, the Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (rho_a), and Composite Reliability (rho_c) values for the three constructs are all > 0.90, thus exceeding the minimum limit of 0.70 recommended in the PLS-SEM analysis. Specifically, the corporate image construct has a Cronbach's Alpha value reaching 0.935, rho_a 0.938, and rho_c 0.953. The purchase intention construct shows a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.931, rho_a 0.931, and rho_c 0.956. On the other hand, the trust construct obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.937, rho_a of 0.938, and rho_c of 0.960. These values indicate that the indicators in each construct have very strong internal consistency and are able to measure the latent construct stably.

Table 6. Reliability Test

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho a)	Composite reliability (rho c)
Corporate Image	0.935	0.938	0.953
Purchase Interest	0.931	0.931	0.956
Trust	0.937	0.938	0.960

Source: Processed data, 2026

Inner Model

A. R-square

Based on the data analysis, the R-Square value for the Purchase Intention variable is 0.699. This explains that the external variables in the model are able to explain 69.9% of the variation in purchase intention, while the remaining 30.1% is influenced by other factors outside this study. The R² value is classified as moderate, in accordance with the PLS-SEM criteria which state that a value > 0.50 indicates that the model has adequate explanatory power. After taking into account the number of predictor variables, the Adjusted R-Square value for purchase intention was recorded at 0.693, which indicates that the model's explanatory power remains open and does not experience significant changes with a small difference (0.006). This indicates that the model does not experience *overfitting* and provides accurate predictions. In addition, the R-Square value for the trust variable was recorded at 0.671, which means that 67.1% of the variation in trust is explained by external variables in the model, while 32.9% is outside the scope of the model. This figure is also in the moderate category, indicating that the independent variables have a significant impact on the formation of trust. The Adjusted R-Square value for trust is 0.668, with a small difference (0.003) compared to the R² value, which confirms that the structural model shows good stability and reliable predictive ability after considering the existing complexity. Therefore, it can be concluded that the applied PLS-SEM structural model has the power to explain and predict both endogenous variables, namely purchase intention and trust.

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Table 7. R-square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Purchase Interest	0.699	0.693
Trust	0.671	0.668

Source: Processed data, 2026

B. F-square

From the f-Square (f^2) analysis, it is explained that each exogenous construct has a different influence on the endogenous construct in this study, which includes purchase intention and trust. The f^2 value serves to assess how much influence an exogenous construct has on increasing the R^2 of the endogenous construct when the construct is included in the research model. Based on the criteria proposed by Cohen (1988), an f^2 value of 0.02 is considered a small effect, 0.15 as a medium effect, and 0.35 as a large effect.

Table 8. F-square

	f-square
Corporate Image -> Purchase Interest	0.230
Corporate Image -> Trust	2,040
Trust -> Purchase Interest	0.191

Source: Processed data, 2026

Inter-Construct Influence

- Corporate Image → Purchase Intention ($f^2 = 0.230$) An f^2 value of 0.230 indicates a moderate influence. This indicates that corporate image plays a significant role in explaining variations in purchase intention. Therefore, a positive view of a company can increase consumer interest in shopping.
- Corporate Image → Trust ($f^2 = 2.040$) The f^2 value of 2.040 is considered to have a very strong influence. This indicates that corporate image plays a very strong role in building trust. The more positive a company's image, the greater the consumer's trust in it.
- Trust → Purchase Intention ($f^2 = 0.191$) The f^2 value of 0.191 falls into the moderate influence category. This indicates that trust has a fairly strong impact on increasing purchase intention, where consumers with high levels of trust tend to be more interested in making a purchase.

The overall f-square analysis results indicate that corporate image is a key construct in the model, particularly in building trust, which subsequently plays a role in increasing purchase intention. Meanwhile, trust has also been shown to be an important mechanism that can strengthen the influence of corporate image on purchase intention. These findings explain that a company's efforts to build a positive image will have a significant impact, both directly and indirectly, on consumer purchase intention.

C. Qpredict

The Q^2 predict test was conducted to evaluate the ability of the structural model to predict variations in observational data on endogenous variables. This test uses the PLSpredict procedure, where a Q^2 predict value > 0 indicates *predictive relevance*, a value > 0.15 reflects moderate predictive power, and a value > 0.35 indicates strong predictive power (Geisser, 1975; Hair et al., 2017). Based on the analysis results, the Q^2 predict values obtained for the endogenous variables are as follows: purchase intention of 0.631 and trust of 0.652. Both values are well above the 0.35 limit, thus indicating that the model has strong predictive ability for both endogenous variables. This high Q^2 predict value indicates that the exogenous constructs in the model are able to accurately predict variations in observational data on purchase intention and trust.

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Table 9. Qpredict

	Q ² predict
Purchase Interest	0.631
Trust	0.652

Source: Processed data, 2026

D. Goodness of Fit (GoF)

Edalmen and Ngadiman (2020) state that the GoF value is obtained from the square root of *the average communalities index* multiplied by the average R² value of the model and spans a range from 0 to 1 with the interpretation of the value divided into three, namely 0.10 (small), 0.25 (medium), and 0.36 (large). This aims to conduct a *Goodness of Fit Index* (GoF) test which aims to validate the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) obtained through the following calculation:

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.868 \times 0.865}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.595}$$

$$GoF = 0.771$$

The Goodness of Fit (GoF) value is obtained by calculating the square root of the product of *the Average Variance Extracted (AVE)* and R² values. With a GoF value recorded at 0.771, this figure exceeds the minimum limit of 0.36 recognized in PLS-SEM as a large category. This indicates that the research model shows a high fit between the measurement and the structural model. More specifically, the AVE value of 0.868 explains that each latent construct in the model has met the requirements of convergent validity, where each construct is able to explain more than 50% of the variance of the indicators that make it up. On the other hand, the R² value of 0.865 indicates that the endogenous variables in the model are significantly explained by the exogenous variables that influence them, so the strength of the structural model can be considered strong. The combination of good convergent validity and high predictive ability of the structural model results in a high GoF value. Therefore, it can be concluded that the PLS-SEM model used in this study shows good to very good overall performance, and can represent empirical data accurately.

Hypothesis Testing (Direct Effect & Indirect Effect)

Table 10. Hypothesis Testing

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Corporate Image -> Purchase Interest	0.459	0.462	0.115	3,995	0.000
Corporate Image -> Trust	0.819	0.822	0.050	16,290	0.000
Trust -> Purchase Interest	0.418	0.414	0.118	3,551	0.000
Corporate Image -> Trust -> Purchase Interest	0.342	0.340	0.100	3,419	0.001

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on the data presented, it can be explained that 4 (four) hypotheses have been accepted with a P-value of 1.65. The first hypothesis that has been tested shows that corporate image has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing interest, with a path coefficient reaching $\beta = 0.459$, a T-statistic value = 3.995, and a p-value = 0.000. In this context, the first hypothesis can be accepted. These results indicate that the better Mayora's corporate image in the eyes of consumers, the higher their purchasing interest in newly launched products, in this case the Gentle Gen product. This finding is in line with the research of Mandagi et al. (2018), which explains that corporate

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image has a positive and significant influence on consumer purchasing desire. The study also concluded that purchasing interest is a behavior that arises as a consumer reaction to an object, which reflects the consumer's desire to transact. In terms of increasing consumer purchasing interest, Mayora needs to focus on developing a good image that includes a positive reputation, social responsibility, transparency, and service quality that can build customer trust. A positive corporate image reflects reputation, credibility, and professionalism, thereby enhancing consumers' perceived value and confidence in purchasing decisions. In a highly competitive business environment, corporate image plays a crucial role, directly influencing consumer interest.

The analysis of the second hypothesis shows that corporate image has a positive and significant influence on consumer trust, with a β value of 0.819, a T-statistic of 16.290, and a p-value of 0.000. Thus, the second hypothesis is accepted. This high coefficient indicates that Mayora's corporate image is highly influential in building consumer trust when they consider purchasing the products offered. The product discussed in this study is Mayora's latest innovation, the Gentle Gen product. These results align with research by Noviningsih (2022), which states that companies with a good image can increase consumer trust. In other words, a positive corporate image can foster consumer trust. A good corporate image indicates that the company has high integrity, quality, and commitment to its consumers. This trust arises because consumers see the company as a reliable entity, providing a sense of comfort, and being able to consistently meet consumer expectations. This situation ultimately becomes the main basis for creating long-term relationships between the company and its consumers.

The third hypothesis shows that trust has a positive and significant impact on purchase intention, with a β value of 0.418, a T-statistic of 3.551, and a p-value of 0.000. Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted. This finding indicates that a higher level of consumer trust is directly proportional to their interest in purchasing Gentle Gen products produced by Mayora. These findings align with the research study by Tiara et al. (2021), which explains that the trust variable has a positive influence on customer purchase intention. The study revealed that the greater the level of consumer trust in Mayora, the higher their purchase intention for Gentle Gen products. Trust plays a crucial psychological role, reducing the perception of risk in the product purchasing process. When consumers feel confident in a company's credibility and stability, they tend to be more open to making purchases. Based on this, trust can be seen as a crucial factor connecting positive consumer views with stronger purchase intention.

indirect effect test on the fourth hypothesis indicate that corporate image has a significant positive influence on purchase intention through trust as a connecting variable, with a β value of 0.342, T-statistic = 3.419, and p-value = 0.001, so this hypothesis is declared accepted. This finding indicates that trust functions as a connecting variable that indirectly links corporate image with purchase intention. In this case, Mayora's positive image not only directly increases purchase intention but also has an indirect impact by increasing consumer trust in the recently launched Gentle Gen product. This role as a connector indicates that built trust is very important in strengthening the effect of corporate image on purchase intention. Research by Khan et al. (2020) emphasizes that trust is the main link between consumer perception and their desire to transact. When consumers have trust in a brand, it will increase their interest in purchasing the product offered. Thus, corporate image can be seen as an initial trigger, while trust is a psychological process that can transform this positive perception into an intention to act and foster purchase intention. Based on these findings, the company's strategy should not only focus on building a positive image, but also need to strive to maintain and increase the level of consumer trust in order to optimize the achievement of purchasing intentions.

This study explains that corporate image has a significant impact on consumer interest in purchasing, with trust as a mediating variable in the launch of the new product Gentle Gen at the company Mayora Indah Tbk. These findings are in line with research conducted by Huang et al. (2019) which explains that a positive corporate image will be embedded in consumers' memories, which will increase their desire to purchase products launched by the company because of a sense of trust in the company. Thus, this study successfully explains that consumer interest in purchasing can be influenced by a good corporate image, and trust functions as a mediator that provides a positive influence between corporate image and consumer purchasing interest. The novelty in this study lies in the focus of the product studied, namely the product Gentle Gen which, a liquid detergent product, is a product newly launched by the company Mayora. In this case, the study also succeeded in filling *the research gap* against previous research that no one has studied *the new product launch*, namely the product Gentle Gen, especially in FMCG companies in Indonesia.

Conclusion

This study successfully answered the research question regarding how a strong corporate image can influence consumer purchasing interest in the new product Gentle Gen. Based on empirical findings, it can be concluded that Mayora's positive corporate image, built through a reputation for product quality, continuous innovation, social

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responsibility, and brand strength, is significantly able to encourage consumer purchasing interest in Gentle Gen even though this product is in a completely new category for the company. The influence of corporate image on purchasing interest is strong and increases significantly when consumers first build trust in the company. Trust acts as a cognitive bridge that connects positive perceptions about the company with the intention to purchase new products. The stronger consumer trust, the greater the effect of reputation transfer from the company to its new products. This research model shows significant predictive power with an R^2 value for the purchase intention variable reaching 0.699 (which means 69.9% of the variation in purchase intention can be explained by corporate image and level of trust) and an R^2 value for trust reaching 0.671 (67.1% of the variation in trust is explained by corporate image). The Goodness of Fit (GoF) value of 0.771 explains that this model has a very good fit and is able to describe the empirical data adequately. Through descriptive analysis, it can be concluded that potential consumers of Gentle Gen are mostly female (67.3%), aged between 26 and 35 years (60.9%), have a Bachelor's degree (70%), and live in urban areas on the island of Java (including West Java, DKI Jakarta, and East Java). This profile reflects a young, intelligent and information-savvy housewife, acting as the main decision-maker in purchasing household goods. This segment shows high brand awareness and is critical in assessing products, but still trusts corporate image as a guide or quick way to deal with new products for which there is limited information.

Research Implications

For Academics

This study successfully addresses *the research gap* identified in the introduction, namely the limited number of empirical studies examining the role of trust as a mediator between corporate image and purchase intention in the context of new product launches in the Indonesian FMCG industry. The finding that trust mediates this relationship with an indirect effect value ($\beta = 0.342$; $p = 0.001$) provides the following empirical evidence:

- Company image and purchasing interest have a relationship that is not only a direct relationship, but also an indirect relationship that requires building trust first.
- The partial mediation model *found* shows that corporate image has a dual power, namely directly encouraging purchase interest through positive associations and reputation, and indirectly through building trust which then transfers this positive perception into an intention to act.

These findings challenge conventional wisdom, which tends to view the relationship between corporate image and purchase intention as a simple, direct relationship. This research demonstrates that trust is not merely a secondary variable but rather an essential psychological mechanism that strengthens the influence of corporate image.

For Companies

This study provides empirical evidence that corporate image is not merely a "complement" in marketing strategy, but rather a strategic asset that has a measurable impact on the acceptance of new products. Trust built through a good corporate image must be maintained and safeguarded with consistent product innovation. This study proves that trust plays a crucial role as a bridge between corporate image and consumer purchasing interest in new Gentle Gen products. This means that Mayora's positive reputation alone is not enough if it is not followed by strengthening trust through concrete actions. In this case, product innovation becomes the link because consumer trust cannot be sustained only by reputation; consumers need tangible evidence that Mayora continues to understand consumer needs and always provides new innovations. Therefore, in this case, Gentle Gen needs to launch new variants with additional benefits.

Research Limitations

This study has several limitations, including methodological ones that must be considered when interpreting the results. First, the research model only includes three main variables: corporate image as the independent variable, trust as the mediating variable, and purchase intention as the dependent variable. This model does not include other factors that could theoretically influence consumer purchase intention at new product launches, such as perceived quality, price, promotion, or consumer attitudes toward the product. These limitations prevent this research model from fully depicting the complexity of consumer behavior in the purchasing decision-making process.

Furthermore, this study employed a quantitative approach with a survey method using an online questionnaire distributed to respondents. Therefore, the data obtained relies heavily on the respondents' subjective perceptions, potentially introducing bias into their responses, such as social bias, when completing the questionnaire. Therefore, further research is recommended to expand the research model by adding other relevant variables to provide a more detailed picture.

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Suggestion

The study found that corporate reputation has a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing intention through corporate image and trust levels. Therefore, companies need to maintain and improve the quality of their products, especially for newly introduced products, to ensure potential consumers feel confident in purchasing. Furthermore, companies must continue to innovate in marketing their products and adapt to current developments to remain competitive. Future research will examine consumer purchasing intention through corporate image, trust, and promotional strategies to increase purchasing intention, particularly during new product launches.

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